

35 filling and packing of jars. In the first step water, vinegar, oil and egg yolk (and optionally
36 flavourings) are mixed together to form a coarse emulsion. In the second step the drop size is
37 further reduced by a high shear mixer to produce a stable product with desired oil droplet size.
38 The high shear mixer used by Dubbelboer et al. (2016) is a cone mill and is produced by IKA
39 Process Technology (2020). It comprises of a rotating frustum surrounded by a gap ($< 1\text{mm}$)
40 produced by a close-fitting stator, an inlet chamber receiving the emulsion and a collecting
41 chamber from where the product is delivered. The cone mill rotation speed and the gap size can
42 be varied to allow the control of shear rate to deliver the target oil droplet size. The desired gap
43 size is obtained by moving the rotor up or down along its axis relative to the stator and rotation
44 speed is controlled by an electric motor.

45 Dubbelboer et al. (2016) sought to correlate the measured drop size with operating conditions
46 (specifically shear rate) and the composition. However, despite extensive evaluation they were
47 unable to obtain a single model that correlated all the data. Their model assumed simple shear
48 in the gap between rotor and stator as the only important hydrodynamic feature. The purpose
49 of our study it to provide a more detailed examination of the hydrodynamics in the gap and the
50 upstream and downstream mixer geometry of the mixer in order to improve the prediction of
51 the drop size.

52 The modelling of the cone mill is a combination of computational fluid dynamics and
53 population balance modelling (PBM). The hydrodynamic field is represented by momentum
54 and continuity conservation and details the local shear rates. The shear rate is then used by the
55 population balance modelling to predict a drop size (Janssen and Mayer (2016) and Janssen and
56 Hoogland (2014)). Power consumption comes from shear and pressure integration and will
57 depend on gap size, viscosity and inlet mass flow rate (e.g. Rapley et al. (2008)). The
58 hydrodynamic analysis is crucial to detecting instabilities occurring in the gap between rotor
59 and stator walls which can make the emulsion preparation hard to control and also to model
60 numerically (Maindarkar et al. (2014)).

61 Tuning of the PBM can be difficult and often it is limited to a fairly narrow operating space.
62 Dubbelboer et al. (2016) were not able to find a universal set of PBM parameters that covered
63 all the data points and our own initial studies (Lupieri et al. (2019)) were able to only partially
64 reproduce the experimental results. Similarly, Ferrari et al. (2020) using open source software
65 were only able to reproduce a few of the results. It was unclear if this was a reflection of the
66 simplified hydrodynamics or the sensitivity to the PBM parameters (Lupieri et al. (2019)). The
67 aim of the present study is therefore to assume the model in Dubbelboer et al. (2016), investigate
68 the CFD, PBM and their coupling to identify a universal set of PBM parameters. It is useful to

69 note that devices for emulsion preparation are frequently designed to perform and produce in
70 predictable conditions: clear gap and nominal shear dependence should be ideally assumed by
71 a factory or pilot plant engineer approaching the production of a good, to establish a priori and
72 control the desired characteristics of a product, for instance the final Sauter mean diameter. This
73 led to accept the simple shear approximation in Dubbelboer et al. (2016) and investigate the
74 effects of geometry instead. Rather than jump straight to the most detailed and hence complex
75 geometry which will require considerable computing power to solve, we start with a very
76 simplified version of the cone mill geometry and then gradually add geometric detail to it. We
77 select the geometries so that we can compare with literature examples of the hydrodynamics
78 modelling to ensure our CFD methodology is consistent with best practice. Having
79 demonstrated this, we then apply the PBM and evaluate the results through comparison with
80 experimental drop size distributions.

81 The topic of the numerical modelling of dispersed system in high shear devices is broad since
82 can cover bubbles or droplets (as in the current work) or even aggregates as in Bałdyga et al.
83 (2007). In that case, the studied device was a Silverson 150/250 which is frequently adopted in
84 emulsion preparation at pilot scale and is intended to be the target of further investigations of
85 the authors of this work, taking advantage from the results of both the mentioned work and the
86 results here presented. In particular, the work of Bałdyga et al. (2007) has shown how the rotor
87 stator configuration was less efficient than a high-pressure nozzle disintegrator system in the
88 breakage process, which was a delicate topic since, at high rotational speed (above 10,000 rpm)
89 and due to the high suction in the rotor proximity, the Silverson 150/250 could develop
90 undesired cavitation, witnessing high pressure drop effects in conjunction with the shear
91 developed between blades and screens leading to possible difficulties in its management.

92 Another crucial aspect in the numerical modelling of the dispersed phase through Population
93 Balance is that it can be subjected to both laminar or turbulent regime of the carrying phase as
94 considered in Bałdyga and Podgórska (2009) where a model for the breakage was developed to
95 include turbulence intermittency. In particular, the drop breakage was discussed in the inertial
96 regime and controlled by Weber number. This is a crucial point since in the same high shear
97 mixers it is possible to have inertial and viscous regimes coexisting and associated to different
98 regions of the device and possibly responding to diverse non dimensional numbers.

99 The numerical analysis of dispersed systems through Population Balance Modelling (PBM)
100 described in Bałdyga et al. (2018) in its general formulation, consists of a nonlinear-integro-
101 partial- differential equation, solved for instance by using the quadrature method of moments
102 (QMOM) as in Jasińska et al. (2014). Among the possible approaches, the S- γ method of

103 moments, as implemented by Lo and Zhang (2009) is adopted here. Due to its standard
 104 formulation, in the followings are reported only the details strictly necessary for the discussion.
 105 The model consists of two transport equations, one for the particle number density n (zeroth
 106 moment, $S=0$) and one for the interfacial area density (second moment, $S=2$).

107 When the phase volume fraction α is also available, the method can deliver the Sauter mean
 108 diameter of a dispersed phase as:

$$109 \quad d_{32} = \frac{6\alpha}{\pi S_2}. \quad (1)$$

110 The general form of the assumed transport equations reads as:

$$111 \quad \frac{dS_\gamma}{dt} = S_{br} + S_{cl}, \quad (2)$$

112 where the balance between droplet breakage and coalescence is expressed in the source term.

113 The coalescence contribute reads as:

$$114 \quad S_{cl} = (2^{\gamma/3} - 2)C_r C_p d_{eq}^\gamma, \quad (3)$$

115 In the current numerical simulations, the dispersed phase is subjected to the viscous regime.

116 Here is reported the corresponding and necessary physics. The collision rate C_r reads as a
 117 function of the dispersed phase fraction ϕ_d and the shear rate $\dot{\gamma}$:

$$118 \quad C_r = K_1 \frac{24\phi_d^2 \dot{\gamma}}{\pi^2 d_{eq}^3}, \quad (4)$$

119 the coalescence probability C_p includes coalescence time scale t_{cl} (drainage time) as:

$$120 \quad C_p = \exp(-K_2 t_{cl} \dot{\gamma}). \quad (5)$$

121 In the current model, the Capillary number is defined as:

$$122 \quad Ca = \frac{\eta_{em} d_{32} \dot{\gamma}}{2\sigma}, \quad (6)$$

123 including apparent emulsion viscosity (further defined) as the emulsion is dense. Breakage
 124 occurs when Capillary number exceeds a critical value. De Bruijn (1989) provided the simple
 125 shear correlation of data in Figure 1, adopted in the current investigation that assumes the model
 126 in Dubbelboer et al. (2016). Nevertheless, when elongational properties are also included, a
 127 smaller critical Capillary number is sufficient for breakage in the same condition of viscosity
 128 ratio. To include this, a flow index ζ is locally defined to identify the flow conditions between
 129 the two extremes: $\zeta = 0$ for simple shear and $\zeta = 1$ for extensional flow: Figure 1 completes
 130 including the data from Bentley and Leal (1989) relative to flow regimes with elongational
 131 effects.

132 For a given particle distribution function $P(d)$, the breakage source term is defined as:

$$133 \quad S_{br} = \int_{d_{\max}}^{\infty} n P(d) b(d) (p^{1-\gamma/3} - 1) d(d), \quad (7)$$

134 with $b(d)$ the breakage frequency. In this work, the definition given by Dubbelboer et al. (2016)
135 is assumed:

$$136 \quad b(d) = \begin{cases} K_3 t_{br}^{-1}, & \text{if } d > d_{\max} \\ 0, & \text{if } d \leq d_{\max} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

137 Where d_{\max} is the maximum stable droplet diameter, t_{br} is the breakage time which is estimated
138 from dimensional analysis in the form:

$$139 \quad t_{br} = \frac{C \eta_{em} d_{32} \lambda^{0.3}}{2\sigma}, \quad (9)$$

140 where $C \cong 60$ has been determined by the experiments of Wieringa et al. (1996). Similar
141 formulations, as for instance in Lo and Zhang (2009), include a polynomial function of viscosity
142 ratio instead of the fitting $\lambda^{0.3}$.

143 The number of fragments originated from the breakage reads as:

$$144 \quad p = 2 + \left(\frac{Ca}{Ca_{crit}} \right)^3. \quad (10)$$

145 Experimentally derived and assumed in the model of Dubbelboer et al. (2016), the number of
146 fragments is a function of the viscosity ratio, mother droplet size and flow conditions, scaling
147 with $(Ca/Ca_{crit})^3$. The addition of 2 is also present in the mentioned implementation to fit with
148 the daughter droplet size distribution in cases of bluntly change between relatively low shear
149 zones (as our inlet) and high shear (as the gap), promoting multiple fragments breakage. The
150 assumption of multiple fragments breakage helps in reaching a maximum steady drop size as
151 soon as the shear rate is sufficient to generate a breakage event, that can occur before the rotor
152 tip is reached.

153 The maximum steady droplets size d_{\max} is calculated as:

$$154 \quad d_{\max} = K_4 \frac{2\sigma Ca_{crit}}{\eta_{em} \dot{\gamma}}, \quad (11)$$

155 where σ is the surface tension, $\dot{\gamma}$ is the shear rate and K_4 is another model parameter. Ca_{crit} is
156 the critical Capillary number evaluated using the correlation of De Bruijn (1989).

157 The parameters K_1, K_2, K_3 and K_4 are adjustable model parameters not present in the original
158 formulation of the method but here included to empirically compensate (to some extent) for the
159 fact that the reference breakup criteria are based on assumption of a single droplet in a steady
160 flow, which could not be quantitatively valid for all the considered cases.

161 The document continues exposing the investigated cases, defines the adopted geometries,
162 rheology and operative conditions. Then, validation and results of the analysis are presented in
163 three parts. Last, the document completes with a conclusion including perspectives and
164 references.

166

167 Figure 1. Capillary number vs viscosity ratio in simple shear and extensional flows. Simple
 168 shear flow as solid circle for $\zeta=0$. Other values of ζ : square (0.2), cross (0.4), plus (0.6), triangle
 169 (0.8) and dot (1).

170

171

172

2. Materials and Methods

173 Three geometries are used in the CFD with increasing complexity. Geometry 1, CG1 in Figure
 174 2(a) is a simple truncated cone acting as a rotor surrounded by a close-fitting stator to produce
 175 a narrow gap and allows for comparison with the numerical simulations of Li et al. (2014),
 176 Ferrari et al. (2020)) and the experiments of Nouimehidi et al. (2005). Li et al. (2014) has an
 177 inner rotating cone and no flow through the mixer, aspect ratio $\Gamma = H/d = 12.5$, radius ratio $\varepsilon =$
 178 $R_1/R_2 = 0.8$, cone inclination angle = 82deg and (rotational) and Reynolds number $Re_r = \frac{dR_1\omega}{\nu}$.

179 The experimental work of Nouimehidi et al. (2005) uses a truncated cone with a maximum
 180 $Re_r = 730$ after a gradual increase of the rotational speed to produce a pattern of rotating
 181 vortices.

182
 183 Figure 2. Topology of all geometries: CG1 on (a), CG2 on (b) and CG3 on (c) with relevant
 184 quantities and probe locations.

object	r_1 (mm)	r_2 (mm)	h (mm)
rotor	23.400	30.000	25.000
gap=0.624 (mm)			
cone2	24.024	30.624	25.000
cone3	17.424	24.024	25.000
cone4	30.624	37.244	25.000
gap=0.208 (mm)			
cone2	23.608	30.208	25.000
cone3	17.008	23.608	25.000
cone4	30.208	36.808	25.000

185 Table 1: Relevant quantities of CG2.

186

187

188 Geometry 2 (CG2) adds shaft and extrusions of the upper and lower chambers as in Figure 2(b)

189 and Table 1. Reference for the problem is in Dubbelboer et al. (2014) and Dubbelboer (2016).

190 Geometry 3 (CG3) of Figure 2(c) reproduces the features of a complex cone mill by including
 191 two grooved blades at the top of rotor in Geometry 2 and the exit pipe is in the side of the outlet
 192 chamber as in IKA (2020).

193 The fluid and drop size properties are taken from Dubbelboer et al. (2016) and are reproduced
 194 in Table 2. The name of every test case from M1S1 to M3S5 will be uniquely defined by
 195 composing the case labels in Table 2.

196 Various models have been proposed for emulsion rheology at high droplet phase fraction, for
 197 instance by Baldyga et al. (2016), but due to its simplicity in implementation and with reference
 198 to Dubbelboer et al. (2016), a Sisko model is used here for the relative viscosity of the
 199 emulsions:

$$200 \quad \eta_R = \eta_{r,\infty} + K(\dot{\gamma})^{-m}, \quad (12)$$

201 where $\eta_{r,\infty}$, K and m depend upon the oil concentration as in Table 2.

202 We adopt the effective medium concept in Jansen et al. (2001) where the emulsion viscosity is
 203 used as the continuous phase viscosity in the single droplet correlations of Grace (1982).
 204 Maindarkar et al. (2014) use this approach to identify the minimum condition leading to the
 205 breakage of an oil droplet in the emulsion.

206 The emulsion is therefore modelled after Park (2018) as a pseudo-single-phase flow obtained
 207 from the two separated phases: the oil phase and the continuous phase which is a "matrix" with
 208 the other mayonnaise ingredients.

209 As a consequence, the two phases will have the same kinematic viscosity but different density:
 210 $\rho_m = 997 \text{ kg/m}^3$ for the matrix and $\rho_o = 917 \text{ kg/m}^3$ for the oil. Similarly, the inlet mass flow
 211 rates of Table 2 will split in proportion to the phase fraction and, after the assumption of Park
 212 (2018), the viscosity of the continuous phase is computed as:

$$213 \quad \frac{\eta_a \eta_R \rho_m}{\phi_m \rho_m + \phi_o \rho_o}, \quad (13)$$

214 while the viscosity of the oil is computed as:

$$215 \quad \frac{\eta_a \eta_R \rho_o}{\phi_m \rho_m + \phi_o \rho_o}, \quad (14)$$

216 where $\eta_a = 0.01 \text{ (Pa.s)}$ is the measured aqueous phase viscosity and $\eta_{em} = \eta_a \eta_R$.

217 From a numerical view point, multiphase flows can be approached as inter-penetrating continua
 218 for which are resolved transport equations for mass, momentum and energy of each phase.
 219 Pressure will be in common for all the phases and when no dependence from temperature is
 220 assumed, the energy balance is not considered. The numerical method here adopted consists of
 221 resolving the hydrodynamics of the problem with a Segregated Finite Volume Navier-Stokes
 222 solver and considering a Population Balance Model (PBM) for the dispersed phase. A transport

223 equation for the volume fraction completes the method. Due to the high viscosity, the regime
 224 does not require a model for turbulence: the Reynolds number calculated as in Dubbelboer et
 225 al. (2016) hardly reaches 200.

226 The numerical method includes the specification of boundary conditions. With reference to
 227 geometry CG1, no-slip on all the fixed surfaces while the inner rotor moves with prescribed
 228 rotational speed.

229 The section completes with the boundary conditions adopted for geometries CG2 and CG3:
 230 fixed mass flow rate at the inlet, zero gradient at the outlet (momentum conservation), fixed
 231 angular velocity at the rotor and shaft, no slip at the external walls. In absence of a fixed pressure
 232 value at the outlet boundary condition and consistently with the adopted solvers, a reference
 233 value for pressure is specified in a single cell within the computing domain.

M-label	ϕ continuous	ϕ oil	d_{32} (μm)	$\eta_{r,\infty}$	K	m
M1	0.35	0.65	37.126	1.0	273	0.49
M2	0.30	0.70	35.776	5.9	1800	0.66
M3	0.25	0.75	23.667	9.0	5600	0.70
S-label	flow rate (kg/h)	rotor speed (rpm)	u_{tip} (m/s)	gap (mm)	shear rate (/s)	t_{res} (s)
S1	31	6039	18.97	0.624	30403	0.31
S2	15	6784	21.31	0.208	102464	0.21
S3	64	3170	9.96	0.624	15959	0.15
S4	15	6039	18.97	0.624	30403	0.64
S5	48	3170	9.96	0.208	47879	0.07

234 Table 2. Simulations executed with reference case label: continuous phase and oil weight
 235 fraction (% w/w), initial oil droplet size and parameters assumed for the corresponding rheology
 236 curves, flow rate, rotor speed, tip velocity, gap size and corresponding shear rate and residence
 237 time.
 238

239

240 3. Results and Discussion

241 This section includes three parts. The first part concerns the study of the hydrodynamics.
 242 Geometry 1 of Figure 2(a) is approached first: validation of results is done against other
 243 numerical simulations and experiments. Subsequently the geometry is extended including upper
 244 and lower chambers (CG2) and the cases in Table 2 are assumed.

245 The second part consists of an extensive study of Population Balance Modelling for CG2. The
 246 last part extends method and Population Balance Model tuning to CG3.

247

248 3.1. Part I

249 3.1.1 Grid generation and independence

250 A grid independence study is conducted for the assumed geometries using case M2S1 as a test
 251 and examining the following physical properties: pressure, shear rate, relative viscosity along
 252 the centre of the gap from bottom to top, vertical velocity component in the radial direction at
 253 half gap. Figure 3 reports the results of the study with an increasing grid resolution and includes
 254 the results of Ferrari et al. (2020), indicated as VIMMP. Quantities are made non dimensional
 255 with atmospheric pressure (p_{Ref}), tip speed (u_{Tip}) and nominal shear rate ($\dot{\gamma}_{ref}$) as in Table 2.
 256 The final grid adopted for Geometry 2 is sketched in Figure 4 and comprised 180 nodes along
 257 the tangential direction (every 2 degrees) and 30x80 in the radial and axial directions of the
 258 rotor.

259

260

261

262 Figure 3. Grid independence study: pressure, vertical component of velocity, relative viscosity
 263 and shear rate on (a), (b), (c) and (d) respectively.

264

268 Figure 4. Sketches of the computing mesh of Geometry 2: outer gap proximity on (a), rotor on
 269 (b) and a general view on (c).

274 **3.1.2 CFD Validation and Verification**

275 Geometry 1 reproduces case CG1 in Li et al. (2014). Instabilities are observed at $Re=192.5$
 276 (Figure 5(a), case vv4 of Table 3): the number of rotating structures corresponds to Li et al.
 277 (2014) with the pressure drop at the middle of the gap reproducing the oscillations as seen in
 278 the literature is reported in Figure 6. Table 3 also reports that, when the boundary conditions
 279 are changed by introducing a mass flow rate or equivalently imposing an inlet velocity from the
 280 top of the geometry, instabilities are suppressed, and the pressure drop decreases and becomes
 281 positive. The cone geometry can act as a centrifugal pump reducing the pressure drop (vv3) but
 282 eventually the pressure drop becomes positive (vv1 and vv2) when the natural pumping
 283 capability is lower than the imposed flow.

284 Geometry 1 also reproduces Nouimehidi et al. (2002) in which the frustum is steadily
 285 accelerated at a rate $\beta = 1.3$ (rad/s²) with a final Re=730. This time the device has a larger
 286 radius at the top than at the bottom and again there is no axial flow at inlet. The numerical
 287 simulation reproduced again the number of vortices of the experiments (8) and their relative
 288 size (smaller at the top of the device). Figure 7(a) presents an isosurface of the flow field which
 289 is similar to Figure 8.3 of Nouimehidi et al. (2002) and a line integral convolution of the
 290 velocity, on (b) are sketched its radial and axial components. Together these two cases indicate
 291 that the set-up of the CFD is correct and in the next section we move to reproduce the conditions
 292 in Dubbelboer et al. (2016).

case	u (m/s)	ω (rad/s)	Δp (Pa)	instability
CG1	-	6×10^{-2}	-3.46×10^{-3}	yes
vv1	1×10^{-2}	1×10^{-2}	$+6.15 \times 10^{-2}$	no
vv2	7×10^{-3}	6×10^{-2}	$+3.85 \times 10^{-2}$	no
vv3	1×10^{-3}	6×10^{-2}	-1.05×10^{-3}	no
vv4	1×10^{-4}	6×10^{-2}	-3.24×10^{-3}	yes
vv5	1×10^{-4}	3×10^{-2}	-5.32×10^{-4}	onset

293 Table 3. Test cases for validation and verification.
 294

295
 296 Figure 5. Line integral convolution of velocity field in case CG1: fully developed Taylor
 297 vortices on (a), instability onset on (b), instability absence on (c).

298

299 Figure 6. Pressure along the gap in current investigation (red crosses) vs reference literature

300 (black line).

301

302 Figure 7. Sketches of velocity fields and flow patterns at $t=30s$: line integral convolution and

303 isosurface on (a), radial and axial components respectively on (b).

304

305

306

307 *3.1.3. Hydrodynamics of the cone mill*

308 This section concerns the hydrodynamics of Geometry 2 extending the modelling of

309 Dubbelboer et al. (2016) which only considers the gap since it is the highest shear region. The

310 presence of a chamber at the top of the rotor allows to include its effect at the gap entry and the

311 chamber at its bottom to include any coalescence effects when the fluid leaves the high shear

312 zone. The gap size remains relatively small when compared to rotor radius so the entire domain
313 can be split into well-defined zones. The first one includes the top chamber where the velocity
314 field shows a centrifugal driven recirculation pattern on the top of the rotor which will increase
315 local shear rates that could lead to droplet breakage before the fluid enters the gap. This is
316 sketched in Figure 8(a). Figure 8(b) and (c) shows how the gap region, dominated by the rotor
317 speed, can be affected also by secondary recirculation seen in the previous section. Diversely,
318 in the original work, Dubbelboer et al. (2016) assumed simple shear rate in their PBM. Finally,
319 the bottom chamber is a low shear rate region which could allow for some coalescence since in
320 practice egg yolk proteins are large and hence slow to diffuse to stabilise the newly created
321 surface in the gap. The shaft in the bottom chamber plays an important role in the
322 hydrodynamics. Its low tip speed will not cause break up but it disrupts quasi stagnant flow in
323 the middle of the chamber: this could pollute the delivered droplet size distribution at the outlet.
324 As a consequence, we see that the upper and lower chambers could have a significant impact
325 on PBM.
326

328 Figure 8. M1S1: line integral convolution of velocity and instabilities in the gap.

329

330 Figure 9 shows the pressure field in which is evidenced the change of sign in pressure drop
331 along the device, depending on operative conditions as considered also in the previous section
332 for Geometry 1, reported in Table 3. In the cases with the larger gap, the device is subjected to
333 positive pressure drop (a), negative in the cases of smaller gap (b).

334 (a) (b)
 335 Figure 9. Examples of pressure fields: case M1S1 on (a) and M2S2 on (b).
 336

337 Figure 10 presents velocity profiles at the top (a), middle (b) and bottom (c) of the gap. The
 338 velocity profile at the gap inlet (a) is a combination of the flow developed in the first chamber
 339 with the one determined by the gap rotation: due to the various combinations of imposed mass
 340 flow rate, rotational speed and gap size, it would have been difficult to foresee and impose a
 341 similar profile in simulations involving a simplified geometry with the gap only as in the
 342 previous section. In most cases the axial flow is not parabolic and exhibits evidence of vortices
 343 in cases M1S1 and M1S4. On (c) the axial velocity is shown to re-enter fluid in the gap. This
 344 effect reduces with the increase of the emulsion viscosity, vanishing in M3.

345 The occurrence of instabilities in concentric cylinders subjected to the rotation of the inner one
 346 and to an imposed axial pressure gradient has been investigated for instance by Lupetow et al.
 347 (1992). Similar cases are often called Taylor Couette Poiseuille (TCP) flows. The axial
 348 Reynolds number is defined as $Re_a = w \cdot gap / v_{em}$ where the velocity w is assumed from the
 349 imposed mass flow rate, v_{em} is an average value in the gap volume, as in Ferrari et al. (2020).
 350 The Taylor number $Ta = r_2 \omega \cdot gap / v_{em}$ is obtained from the rotational speed. Figure 11 presents a
 351 map (Re , Ta) which illustrates the role of flow rate on suppressing the instabilities in the gap
 352 and returning to a simple shear rate field. Lupetow et al. (1992) used linear stability calculations
 353 to obtain a value for the transition to Taylor vortex flow for the case of zero axial flow of $Ta =$
 354 108, which is similar to the results of the current computations, reproduced in Figure 11. The

355 map here reported shows how the presence of an axial flow can delay instability occurrence:
 356 for example, the pair ($Re=0.5$, $Ta=141$) still represents a stable condition. The map is enriched
 357 with the indication of instability onsets, detected visually as a single vortex at the end of the
 358 gap, as sketched of Figure 5(b).

359 Figure 11 completes with a straight line limiting steady and unsteady regimes. In this case, no
 360 comparison is directly possible with Figure 4 and 6 of Lupetow et al. (1992) for two reasons:
 361 in the first one, a broader range of Reynolds and Taylor numbers was assumed with a
 362 consequent coarse resolution in the niche considered in the current investigation and in the
 363 second one, Lupetow et al. (1992) evidenced how geometry of the problem resulted very
 364 sensitive to radii ratio but assumed cases not directly comparable with the current one.

367 Figure 10: Mayo M1 to M3 in columns: axial velocity component at the inlet (a), half height
 368 (b) and outlet (c) of the gap.

370 Finally, power draw is considered briefly here: not surprisingly for a highly viscous flow, the
 371 majority of the power comes almost entirely from viscous contributes and not from the integral
 372 of pressure at the rotor surface. Consequently, in spite of the small size of the device the high
 373 phase volume emulsion viscosity pushes the power up to 1KW (Table 4).

375

376
 377 Figure 11. Taylor vs Reynolds number: + indicates the presence of developed Taylor vortices
 378 in the gap, lower triangles indicate instability onset.
 379

	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
M1	119.5	226.1	33.0	121.4	54.6
M2	262.0	662.4	74.6	261.7	150.3
M3	412.6	1023.3	135.7	412.4	253.3

380 Table 4. Geometry 2: power (W) calculated at the rotor from torque and pressure contributes.
 381
 382

383 3.2. Part II

384 Optimisation of PBM model parameters is generally affordable when the flow field is either
 385 assumed homogeneous by volume-averaging (so-called 0D lumped PBM) or by introducing a
 386 limited degree of flow inhomogeneity (e.g. PDF-based Buffo et al. (2016), 1D Håkansson et al.
 387 (2009) and zonal PBM Alopaeus et al. (1999)). However, optimising model parameters in
 388 coupled CFD-PBM simulations is computationally intensive. In this exploration, model
 389 parameters are varied by several orders of magnitude, to cover a broad range of parameter
 390 space, while a limited number of values for each parameter is explored. The aim here is to
 391 identify the raw trends of the adopted modelling approach rather than to provide a best fit.

392 Parameter K_4 relates the critical Capillary number to the maximum steady droplet size, and it
 393 is possibly the only parameter that can be experimentally validated in a direct manner. From
 394 the effective medium “Grace model” in Jansen et al. (2001), it can be estimated as $K_4 \sim O(1)$.
 395 Some numerical studies Dubbelboer et al. (2016) have adopted this approach, by setting $K_4=1$,
 396 while in other studies K_4 has been treated as a free parameter (Maindarkar et al. (2014)). Our
 397 preliminary simulations showed that, for $K_4 = 1$, predictions for the 65wt% mayonnaise were

398 insensitive to all operational conditions. A similar trend was observed in Dubbelboer et al.
399 (2016) where the same value was used. By allowing smaller values, the droplet sizes for the 65
400 wt% mayonnaise became sensitive to operational conditions and improved predictions. In this
401 study, we explored different values of $K_4=0.04, 0.4, 1$ and 4 , therefore broadening the
402 investigation space with respect to the range expected from Jansen et al. (2001).

403 For parameter K_2 , previous studies have reported values which span many orders of magnitude
404 in range $10^{-3} - 10^{10}$ (Dubbelboer et al. (2014) and Dubbelboer et al. (2016)). We explored
405 three different values $K_2=0.01, 1, 100$. In the conceptual framework of a binary collision, as
406 worked out by Chesters et al. (1991), it is depicted that, as the film drainage takes substantially
407 longer than the collision time ($1/\dot{\gamma}$) there should be no coalescence, while coalescence is
408 expected in the opposite limit. This behaviour is exactly captured for $K_2=1$, whereas
409 substantially different values of K_2 likely signify break-down of the binary collision assumption
410 in concentrated emulsions.

411 Parameter K_1 controls the magnitude of coalescence frequency. For each pair of values of K_2
412 and K_4 , the relative effect of coalescence was examined by using increasing values of K_1 .
413 Finally, for each K_1, K_2 and K_4 triplet, K_3 was estimated from the out flow d_{32} of test case M3S2
414 and then, the complete set of parameters was used to predict the rest of the test cases. This
415 approach yielded a total number of $3 \times 4 \times 5 = 60$ sets of model parameters, which is a compromise
416 between sufficient exploration of the parameter space and computational cost.

417

418 **3.2.1. Comparisons with experiment**

419 Sauter mean diameters at the outlet of the device obtained from the simulations are compared
420 with the experiment via the parity plot in Figure 12(a). The predictions for test cases S1-S3 are
421 found in reasonable agreement for all three types of mayonnaise. For these test cases, the
422 maximum absolute relative error is 28.92% and the average absolute relative error is 10.25%.
423 Predictions for test cases S4-S5 are weaker as the droplet size is underpredicted. Improved
424 predictions for cases S4-S5 could be obtained but for significantly smaller values of K_1 and K_3
425 in Figure 12(b). In that case, though, agreement for S1-S3 deteriorated and, thus, the overall
426 difference of the simulation results with the experiment was larger than the one obtained using
427 large values of K_1 and K_3 . Using these small values of K_1 and K_3 and for S4-S5, the maximum
428 absolute relative error is 10.01% and the average absolute relative error is 6.96%.

429 From case S1 to case S3, the gap shear rate is varied within its entire range by changing the
430 rotation speed and the gap width. However, the gap residence time is limited to the middle of
431 the range explored (Table 2). Conversely, in S4-S5 the gap residence time covers the whole

432 while the gap shear rate is limited to middle of the range explored. The numerical simulations
433 revealed that two set of model parameters are needed to reproduce the experimental results with
434 the desired accuracy. Each set corresponds to the test cases where either the gap shear rate or
435 the gap residence time is varied the most. The values of these two sets of parameters are reported
436 in Table 5. There doesn't seem to be an obvious explanation of this behaviour which we consider
437 characteristic of the adopted modelling approach, i.e. the combination of the models of breakage
438 frequency, coalescence frequency and daughter size distribution used in this work.

439 The value of K_4 which produced best predictions ($=0.4$) was found smaller than the one
440 established by several experimental studies (≈ 1) (Grace (1982), DeBruijn (1989), Jansen et al.
441 (2001)) but within the same order of magnitude. A likely explanation is the contribution of
442 elongational flow to droplet breakup in colloid mills. The flow field in colloid mills is often
443 idealised as simple shear (Maindarkar (2014), Dubbelboer (2016)), which probably holds in the
444 middle of the gap for sufficiently small Taylor numbers, but it is less likely to hold at the top of
445 the rotor, where the flow accelerates to enter the gap, as well as the gap exit where the flow
446 discharges to the outlet chamber. Experimental studies for elongational flow have identified
447 critical Capillary numbers smaller and of the same order of magnitude than those in simple
448 shear Grace (1982), thereby the value of $K_4=0.4$ can be attributed to the combined effect of
449 simple shear and elongational flow on droplet breakup.

450 In the next section, we analyse the spatial distribution of the droplet sizes obtained using the
451 parameter values in Table 5 for test cases S1-S3.

452

Set	Test Cases	K_1	K_2	K_3	K_4
1	S1-S3	0.0014	0.01	0.11	0.4
2	S4-S5	0.0004	0.01	0.005	0.4

453 Table 5. Optimised parameter values for the test cases where the gap shear rate is varied and
454 the gap residence time is constant (Set 1) and the gap residence time is varied and the gap shear
455 rate is constant (Set 2).

456

457

458 Figure 12: Parity plot of d_{32} using two sets of model parameters shown in Table 4: Set 1 on
 459 (a) and Set 2 on (b). Simulation labels refer to Table 2.

460

461

462 3.2.2. Droplet dispersion

463 The velocity field is dominated by the tangential velocity component imposed by the rotor and
 464 the shaft; the axial and the radial components remain 1-2 orders of magnitude smaller. Despite
 465 their small magnitude, these secondary motions are of great importance because they determine
 466 the residence times at the different compartments of the device. Figure 13(a) shows the d_{32}
 467 contour on the vertical plane for the 70 wt% mayonnaise and operating condition S1. Two
 468 recirculation regions were observed in the chambers above and below the gap. The secondary
 469 flow on this plane is shown in Figure 13(b). Half planes are only shown due to symmetry. In
 470 the top chamber and above the recirculation zone the droplet size increases near the wall of the
 471 inlet chamber due to coalescence. Coalescence is favoured near the wall because of finite shear
 472 rates which are small enough so as not to promote breakage. An increase of d_{32} in this region
 473 was observed in all the test cases examined. Note that the maximum contour level in Figure
 474 13(a) has been adjusted to $40\mu\text{m}$ to facilitate visualisation of d_{32} . For this case, $d_{32,max} = 83.2\mu\text{m}$
 475 observed at the location where the flow detaches from the wall of the inlet chamber. The largest
 476 $d_{32,max}$ among all test cases was $152.9\mu\text{m}$, meaning that the predicted droplet sizes remained
 477 within physical bounds. The recirculation region is due to the drag on the rotating top of the
 478 rotor and centrifugal forces initiating the flow. The high local shear rates cause droplet breakup.
 479 At the gap entrance it splits into two streams: one entering the gap and one directed towards the
 480 recirculation region.

481 Breakage frequency shown in Figure 14(a) suggests that breakage occurs inside the gap, in the
482 boundary layers at the top and the bottom of the rotor, in a small part of the recirculation regions
483 and to a limited extent close to the shaft. The number of fragments (Equation 10), shown in
484 Figure 14(b) peaks at the entrance of the gap, where large droplets encounter large shear.
485 Consequently, the largest change in droplet size is observed in the vicinity of the entry into the
486 gap rather than in the middle region where the flow is expected to be closer to simple shear;
487 this observation is consistent with the earlier explanation that the low value of $K_4 < 1$ is likely to
488 be a contribution of elongational and shear flow to droplet breakup. On the other hand,
489 coalescence is predicted in a much wider part of the domain. Coalescence frequency $C = C_r \cdot$
490 C_p (Equations 4 and 5) is shown in Figure 15; it is maximum in the gap and of considerable
491 magnitude in the recirculation region of the inlet chamber and the entire outlet chamber.

492 Table 6 includes the predicted d_{32} for M2S1 at several locations of the domain; probe locations
493 are visualised in Figure 2(b). At the entrance of the gap, $d_{32} = 8\mu\text{m}$ which means that substantial
494 breakage is predicted upstream since d_{32} at the inlet = $36\mu\text{m}$. Drop size reduces continuously
495 along the gap towards its smallest value in the domain ($3.6\mu\text{m}$) at the gap walls near the bottom.
496 The reduction rate is larger closer to the top of the gap than closer to the bottom (see zoom in
497 Figure 13(a), a Taylor vortex is observed near the gap exit (see zoom in Figure 13(b)).
498 Figure 13(a) further shows an increase in d_{32} from the gap exit to the outlet of the domain.
499 Droplets passing through the recirculation region in the outlet chamber coalesce due to finite
500 shear rates close to the shaft and the rotor bottom surface. Physically this may in part also be
501 due to the slow diffusion of the egg yolk emulsifier to the newly created surfaces though this is
502 not explicitly incorporated in the PBM equations. These droplets are driven back into the shear
503 layer which develops from the rotor bottom edge, and they are dragged downstream by the
504 stream of freshly broken droplets exiting the gap. The volume of the recirculation region in the
505 outlet chamber is expected to affect d_{32} at the outlet, since, for a larger volume of this
506 recirculation region, more droplets will be subject to conditions which promote coalescence. In
507 Figure 13(a), the size of recirculation region in the outlet chamber is indicated via a red
508 streamline, which is the streamline passing through the location at the outlet where the flow
509 reverses. Identifying the size of the recirculating region in the outlet chamber will be useful in
510 the following sections where we compare different test cases. At the same time, a non-
511 recirculating region, relatively smaller in size is present and represents the alternative and
512 preferred way by which droplets can exit more quickly.

513

Location	$d_{32}(\mu\text{m})$				
	M2S1	M1S1	M3S1	M2S2	M2S3
Inlet	35.766	37.126	23.667	35.766	35.766
Rotor Top	18.151	28.781	11.538	12.003	21.932
Gap Top	8.041	11.304	6.658	5.117	20.196
Gap Middle	3.694	5.158	3.448	1.667	7.079
Gap Bottom	3.609	4.914	3.272	1.603	5.151
Outlet	6.259	9.293	5.041	5.624	7.728
Outlet (EXP)	6.587	7.206	4.647	5.844	7.713

514
515
516
517

Table 6. d_{32} at the locations sketched in Figure 2(b) for indicated emulsion and operational conditions. The value of d_{32} is uniform at the inlet and surface average at the outlet.

518
519

Figure 13: (a) Contour of d_{32} and (b) streamlines for test case M2S1; $d_{32,EXP} = 6.587 \mu\text{m}$.

522 Figure 14: Contours of (a) breakage frequency and (b) number of fragments for test case M2S1.

530

531

532 Figure 15: Contour of coalescence frequency for test case M2S1.

533

534

535

536

537

538

539

540

541 **3.2.3. Droplet dispersions for different wt% emulsions and same operational condition**

542 Figures 16 and 17 show contours of d_{32} for the 65 wt% and the 75 wt% emulsion respectively,
543 and S1 operational condition. Values of d_{32} at several locations are reported in Table 6. In the
544 inlet chamber, the effect of increasing wt%, i.e. of increasing viscosity, is to: (i) decrease the
545 size of the recirculation region, (ii) decrease d_{32} at the centre of the rotor top surface and (iii)
546 decrease the d_{32} at the entrance of the gap. The larger viscosity of the higher phase volume
547 emulsions increases the stresses which in turn enhances breakage in the boundary layer on the
548 rotor top surface and thereby reduces the drop size. The reduction of d_{32} inside the gap is also
549 significantly different; for the 75 wt% emulsion, the smallest d_{32} is much closer to the entrance
550 than for the 65 wt% emulsion. This may be because the lower stresses (see above) but also we
551 see Taylor vortices will tend to reduce the local shear rates so the breakup is not as efficient. In
552 the outlet chamber, the increase of d_{32} from the gap exit to the outlet of the domain for the 65
553 wt% emulsion is larger than the one for the 75 wt% emulsion. This appears to be related to the
554 size and shape of the recirculation region which acts as a source of coalescence. The larger
555 viscosity of the 75 wt% emulsion produces a smaller recirculation zone which will reduce the
556 residence time in the bottom chamber for coalescence to occur. In addition, there is a thicker
557 higher shear layer on the underside of the rotor (see Figure 17(b)) which will increase the shear
558 rates promoting breakup compared to the respective shear layer of the 65 wt% emulsion (see
559 Figure 16(b)).

560

561

562

563

564

565

566

567

568

569

570 Figure 16: (a) Contour of d_{32} and (b) streamlines for test case M1S1; $d_{32,EXP} = 7:206 \mu\text{m}$.

571

572

573

574

575

576

577

578

579

Figure 17: (a) Contour of d_{32} and (b) streamlines for test case M3S1; $d_{32,\text{EXP}}=4.647 \mu\text{m}$.

580

581

582

583

584

585

586

587

588

589 **3.2.4. Droplet dispersions for same emulsion and different operational conditions**

590 Figures 18 and 19 show contours of d_{32} for the 70 wt% emulsion and operational conditions S2
591 and S3, respectively. Values of d_{32} at several locations of the two domains are reported in Table
592 6. In S2, the gap shear rate is significantly larger than that in S3 while the gap residence time is
593 similar. Despite the gap shear rate in S3 being 6 times smaller than in S2, with viscosity as in
594 Equation 10, the delivered d_{32} for S3 is only 1.4 times larger than in S2. In the inlet chamber,
595 the effect of increasing flow rate is to suppress the recirculation region, similarly to the effect
596 of increasing viscosity. The value of d_{32} at the entrance of the gap is much larger for S3; this is
597 due to different shear rates in the boundary layer on the top of rotor as driven by the assigned
598 rotational speed. Once the fluid has reached the gap, for S2 the minimum drop size is achieved
599 closer to the gap entrance than for S3. In part this is because it was already smaller on entry
600 but also because the higher gap shear rate. At the gap exit, d_{32} is $1.6\mu\text{m}$ for S2 and $5.1\mu\text{m}$ for
601 S3.

602 The values of d_{32} at the outlet are $5.6\mu\text{m}$ and $7.7\mu\text{m}$, respectively so there is more coalescence
603 in S2. A comparison between Figures 18(b) and 19(b) shows that S2 has a larger recirculation
604 zone and a thinner layer of high shear near the underside of the rotor. This is consistent with
605 the results with the previous section suggesting that a larger recirculation zone of modest shear
606 rates allows coalescence to occur.

607

608

609

610

611

612

613

614

615

616

617 Figure 18: (a) Contour of d_{32} and (b) streamlines for test case M2S2; $d_{32,\text{EXP}} = 5.844 \mu\text{m}$.

618

619

620

621

622

623

624
 625
 626
 627
 628
 629
 630
 631
 632

Figure 19: (a) Contour of d_{32} and (b) streamlines for test case M2S3; $d_{32,\text{EXP}} = 7.713 \mu\text{m}$.

633 **3.3. Part III**

634 The final geometry is CG3 in Figure 2(c) which includes two large grooved blades at its top.
635 Their presence can affect the hydrodynamics in the inlet chamber: Figures 20(a) and (b)
636 evidence the presence of a (permanent) rotating structure at the tip of the two rotor teeth that
637 can extend downwards where there is space between the teeth.

638 Diversely, as sketched in Figure 8, in CG2 a similar feature was present at the flat top of the
639 rotor and was identified as responsible for the recirculation of material in the inlet chamber. In
640 the exit chamber the recirculation zones are still present but this time the exit is lateral.

641

644 Figure 20: Geometry 3: line integral convolution of the velocity field and streamlines on xz
645 plane (a) and on yz plane (b).

646

647 The velocity pattern is dominated in amplitude by the tangential component of the velocity
648 while the axial component reveals a new mechanism that drives the fluid towards the gap.
649 Figure 21 presents axial velocity component in two selected planes, at the top of the blade (a)
650 and at half height (b). The fluid is pushed towards the gap mainly in two specific regions: at the
651 leading edge of the blades (a) and down along the grooves (b), resulting in the complex
652 recirculation pattern in the top chamber.
653

654 (a) (b)
655 Figure 21: Case M1S1, axial velocity at $z=0.025(m)$ on (a) and $z=0.035(m)$ on (b). Rotor is
656 turning anti clockwise.

657
658 Power consumption of Geometry 3 is reported for completeness of analysis in Table 7. In this
659 case, the volume of fluid moved by rotor now includes the part processed by the blades and for
660 this reason the final power consumption is 30-60% higher than in Geometry 2, Table 4. The
661 presence of the blades and teeth increases the surface of rotor in contact with the fluid.
662 Furthermore, the rotor teeth are subjected to a pressure difference between leading and trailing
663 edges, similarly to the case of a blade subjected to an incident flow, suggesting that when
664 pressure is included in the total power calculated on the rotor, it would be always higher than
665 that for Geometry 2 in which pressure contributes were negligible.

666 The results of the population balance modelling are reported in Figure 22 and with reference to
667 Table 5. As in the previous sections we could not get a unique set of tuning parameters and we
668 see two groupings, cases S4 and S5 and then cases S1 to S3. Since the nominal shear (the one
669 at the tip of the rotor base) is unchanged in Geometry 2 and Geometry 3, the small differences
670 with the results in Figure 12 cannot suggest any modelling dependence if not strictly related to
671 the different assumed geometry.

672
673

	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
M1	184.5	505.7	57.7	184.1	123.5
M2	463.8	1475.5	140.0	463.4	336.8
M3	775.5	2290.2	240.3	755.2	524.3

674
675
676

Table 7. Geometry 3: power (W) calculated at the rotor from torque and pressure contributes.

677
678
679
680
681

Figure 22: Parity plot of d_{32} using two sets of model parameters shown in Table 5. Simulation labels refer to Table 2.

Conclusion

682 The motivation of the work is to improve the prediction of emulsion drop size produced by a
683 cone mill. It is intended to be preliminary to further studies on other high shear rotor stator
684 devices. The assumption of most previous workers is that the gap which has by far the highest
685 shear rates dominates the drop size reduction. However, for the cone mill two correlations were
686 required, one for similar gap shear rate and the other for similar residence times (Dubbelboer
687 et al. (2016)). In this study we start from this simplified geometrical view and systematically
688 review the hydrodynamics and the impact on the population balance modelling as we add
689 geometric features. The simplest geometry of a gap shows that the flow is not always simple
690 shear with Taylor-Couette vortices forming at larger gaps and rotor speed though they are
691 suppressed by increasing flow rate. Adding a top chamber produces a recirculation due to
692 centrifugal drag forces which can produce significant drop size reduction before the fluid even
693 enters the gap. Adding the large blades in the entry chamber disrupts this flow adding swirl but
694 the shear between these blades and wall can cause drop break-up. Adding an exit chamber
695 allows coalescence to occur and is related to the size of the recirculation zone. Despite this
696 wealth of additional hydrodynamic features there was, unfortunately, little improvement to the

697 quality of the prediction. This led to the view that the weak link is the PBM. More specifically
698 it would be worth considering elongational and shear driven processes separately, for example
699 K_4 was lower than expected suggesting a more effect breakup mechanism, such as elongational
700 flows, on entry to the gap. This could account for the effect of the residence time grouping since
701 this is related to flow rate and hence extensional flow into the gap. Moreover, the coalescence
702 models are based on the draining of the interstitial fluid in dilute emulsions (Chesters, 1991)
703 whereas in high phase volume emulsions the drops are almost touching and there is nowhere
704 for the fluid to drain and so the physical basis for the constants is questionable. Consequently,
705 there remain exciting scientific challenges in extending the foundational work in PBM of
706 pioneers such as Prof. Bałdyga to products and process of industrial importance.

707

708

709

Nomenclature

710 α – volume fraction

711 $b(d)$ – breakage frequency

712 $\dot{\gamma}$ – shear rate (/s)

713 C – breakage time constant (non-dimensional)

714 Ca – capillary number

715 Ca_{crit} – critical capillary number

716 C_r – coalescence collision rate per unit volume ($\text{m}^{-3} \text{s}^{-1}$)

717 C_p – coalescence probability

718 d_{32} – Sauter mean diameter of oil droplets (m)

719 d_{eq} – equivalent diameter (m)

720 d_{MAX} – maximum steady droplet size (m)

721 η_{em} – apparent emulsion viscosity (Pa.s)

722 η_a – aqueous phase viscosity (Pa.s)

723 η_R – relative viscosity

724 $\eta_{r,\infty}$ – high shear plateau viscosity (Pa.s)

725 K – consistency

726 K_1, K_2, K_3, K_4 – tuning parameters

727 m – fit exponent

728 $P(d)$ – particle size distribution

729 p – number of fragments

730 Re_a – axial Reynolds number
731 ρ_m – density of continuous phase (kg/m³)
732 ρ_o – density of oil (kg/m³)
733 S – moment of S- γ method
734 S_{br}, S_{cl} – breakage and coalescence source terms
735 Ta – Taylor number
736 t_{br} – breakage time (s)
737 t_{cl} – drain time (s)
738 ϕ_m – matrix phase fraction
739 ϕ_o – oil phase fraction

740

741

742 *Subscripts*

743 $\gamma=0, 2, 3$ - number of moments in S- γ method.

744

745

746

Acknowledgements

747 This work was carried out in the context of the VIMMP project (www.vimmp.eu). The VIMMP
748 project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation
749 programme under grant agreement No 760907.

750

751

References

752 Alopaeus, V., Koskinen, J. and Keskinen, K.I., 1999. Simulation of the population balances for
753 liquid-liquid systems in a nonideal stirred tank. Part 1 Description and qualitative validation
754 of the model. *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, 54(24), 5887-5899. DOI: 10.1016/S0009-2509(99)00170-0.
755 Bałdyga, J., Orciuch, W., Makowski, Ł., Malski-Brodzicki, M. and Malik, K., 2007. Break up
756 of nano-particle cluster in high-shear devices. *Chem. Engin. and Processing: Process*
757 *Intensification*. 46 (9), 851-861. DOI: 10.1016/j.cep.2007.05.016.
758 Bałdyga, J., Jasińska, M. and Kowalski, A.J., 2016. Effect of rheology of dense emulsions on
759 the flow structure in agitated systems. *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*. 108, 3-
760 12. DOI: 10.1016/j.cherd.2015.11.026.

761 Bałdyga, J., Jasińska, M., Kotowicz, M., Tyl, G. and Bouaifi, M., 2018. Population Balance
762 Equations: fundamentals, challenges, application, limitations and perspectives. Conference:
763 23rd International Congress of Chemical and Process Engineering. CHISA 2018, Prague.

764 Bałdyga, J. and Podgórska, W., 2009. Drop break-up in intermittent turbulence: Maximum
765 stable and transient sizes of drops. *The Canadian Journal of Chemical Engineering*. DOI:
766 10.1002/cjce.5450760316.

767 Bentley and Leal, 1986. An experimental investigation of drop deformation and breakup in
768 steady, two-dimensional linear flows. *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 167, 241-283.

769 Buffo, A., De Bona, J., Vanni, M. and Marchisio, D. L., 2016. Simplified volume-averaged
770 models for liquid-liquid dispersions: Correct derivation and comparison with other
771 approaches. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 153, 382-393. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2016.07.032.

772 Chesters, A.K. 1991. Modelling of coalescence processes in fluid-liquid dispersions. A review
773 of current understanding, *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, 69(4), 259-227.

774 De Bruijn, R., 1989. Deformation and Breakup of Drops in Simple Shear Flow. *Ph.D. thesis*,
775 Technical University of Eindhoven.

776 Dubbelboer, A., Janssen, J., Hoogland, H., Mudaliar, A., Maindarkar, S., Zondervan, E. and
777 Meuldijk, J., 2014. Population balances combined with computational fluid dynamics: A
778 modeling approach for dispersive mixing in a high-pressure homogenizer. *Chemical*
779 *Engineering Science*, 117, 376-388. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2014.06.047.

780 Dubbelboer A., 2016. Towards optimization of emulsified consumer products: modelling and
781 optimization of sensory and physicochemical aspects. *Ph.D. thesis*, Technical University of
782 Eindhoven.

783 Dubbelboer, A., Janssen, J.J.M., Hoogland, H., Zondervan, E. and Meuldijk, J., 2016. Pilot-
784 scale production process for high internal phase emulsions: Experimentation and modeling.
785 *Chemical Engineering Science*, 148, 32-43. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2016.03.014.

786 Ferrari, M., Boccardo, G., Buffo, A., Vanni, M. and Marchisio, D.L., 2020. CFD-PBM
787 simulation of a high-shear mixer for food emulsion production. To appear on *Canadian Journal*
788 *of Chemical Engineering*.

789 Grace, H.P., 1982. Dispersion phenomena in high viscosity immiscible fluid systems and
790 application of static mixers as dispersion devices in such systems. *Chem. Eng. Commun.*, 14,
791 (3-6), 225-277.

792 IKA, 2020. Commercial Brochure. www.ikaprocess.com.

793 Jansen, K.M.B., Agterof, W.G.M. and Mellema, J., 2001. Droplet breakup in concentrated
794 emulsions. *J. Rheol.* 45, 227-236.

795 Janssen, J.J.M. and Hoogland, H., 2014. Modelling strategies for emulsification in industrial
796 practice. *Can. J. Chem. Eng.* 92, 198-202. DOI: 10.1002/cjce.21942.

797 Janssen, J.J.M. and Mayer, R., 2016. Computational Fluid Dynamics-Based Droplet Size
798 Estimates in Emulsification Equipment. *Processes*, 4, 50; DOI:10.3390/pr4040050.

799 Jasińska, M., Bałdyga, J., Hall, S., Pacek, A. and Andrzej W., 2014. Dispersion of oil droplets
800 in rotor-stator mixers: Experimental investigations and modelling. *Chemical Engineering
801 and Processing: Process Intensification*. 84. 45-53. DOI: 10.1016/j.cep.2014.02.008.

802 Li, X., Zang, J.J. and Xu, Lan-Xi, 2014. A numerical investigation of the flow between rotating
803 conical cylinders of two different configurations. *Journal of Hydrodynamics*, 26(3):431-435.
804 DOI: 10.1016/S1001-6058(14)60049-4.

805 Lo, S. and Zhang, D., 2009. Modelling of Break-up and Coalescence in Bubbly Two-Phase
806 Flows. *Journal of Computational Multiphase Flows*, 1, 23-38. DOI:
807 10.1260/175748209787387106.

808 Lupetow, R.M, Doctor, A. and Min, K., 1992. Stability of axial flow in an annulus with a
809 rotating inner cylinder. *Physics of Fluids A: Fluid Dynamics* 4, 2446.

810 Lupieri, G., Kowalski, A.J., and Janssen, J.J.M., 2019. Numerical modelling of emulsion
811 preparation through CFD. ECCE12, 12th European Congress of Chemical Engineering.

812 Håkansson, A, Trägårdh, C., and Bergenståhl, B., 2009. Studying the effects of adsorption,
813 recoalescence and fragmentation in a high-pressure homogenizer using a dynamic
814 simulation model. *Food Hydrocolloids* 23(4), 1177-1183. DOI:
815 10.1016/j.foodhyd.2008.10.003.

816 Maindarkar, S., Dubbelboer, A., Meuldijk, J., Hoogland, H. and Henson, M., 2014. Prediction
817 of emulsion drop size distributions in colloid mills. *Chemical Engineering Science*, 118,
818 114-125. DOI: 10.1016/j.ces.2014.07.032.

819 Noui-Mehidi, M.N., Ohmura, N. and Kataoka, K., 2002. Mechanism of mode selection for
820 Taylor vortex flow between coaxial conical rotating cylinders. *Journal of Fluids and
821 Structures*, 16(2), 247-262. DOI: 10.1006/jfls.2001.0417.

822 Noui-Mehidi, M.N., Ohmura, N. and Kataoka, K., 2005. Dynamics of the helical flow between
823 rotating conical cylinders. *Journal of Fluids and Structures*, 20(3), 331-344. DOI:
824 10.1016/j.jfluidstructs.2004.12.001.

825 Park, H.M., 2018. Comparison of the pseudo-single-phase continuum model and the
826 homogeneous single-phase model of nanofluids. *International Journal of Heat and Mass
827 Transfer*, 120, 106-116. DOI: 10.1016/j.ijheatmasstransfer.2017.12.027.

828 Rapley, S., Eastwick, C., and Simmons, K., 2008. Computational investigation of torque on
829 coaxial rotating cones. *J. Fluid Eng.* 130, 061102. DOI: 10.1115/1.2903518.
830 Wieringa J.A., Van Dieren F., Janssen J.J.M and Agterof W.G.M., 1996. Droplet breakup
831 mechanism during emulsification in colloid mills at high dispersed phase volume fraction.
832 *Trans IChemE*, Vol 74, part A, 554-562.
833